

ANALYSING THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS CREATIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393746>

The research on the creative development of contemporary most students are relevant because of the changes occurring in the social, political, economic, and cultural domains of society; the trend toward a "knowledge society"; the growing importance of education and science in the modern world; and the rise in employer demands for the caliber and extent of employee training. One of the most well-liked research topics for sociologists, psychologists, and managers is creativity. Since the creation of new concepts and inventive products is the foundation for the growth and establishment of the post-industrial economy, the significance of these studies cannot be overstated. The use of human abilities and skills serves as the foundation for the creation of any product or ideas. Consequently, the growth of creativity is a requirement for the business's financial and social success in the marketplace, as well as for the competitiveness of national economies at the state and global levels. Diverse fields are forming interest in the growth of creativity. Creative thinking is one of the traits that make up the "4C" model, which stands for critical thinking, cooperation, creativity, and communication. These traits were therefore designated as the essential human qualities of the twenty-first century. The need for the development of creativity as part of its integration into the process of academic education and professional training is emphasized which recognizes creativity as one of the key skills required in modern life.

The four primary attributes of creativity are originality, fluency, adaptability, and accuracy. Creativity is defined as a multipurpose cognitive creative talent . Expanding to information which are given in some literature creativity as the expression of problem-sensitivity, ignorance, discord, questing for explanations and solutions, advancing theories, confirming them, and producing outcomes . Maslow links creativity to an individual's needs, stating that the more demands there are, the more creative a person will be. Scientists highlights the link between social values and creativity. The desire for self-expression, self-growth, and potential development is one of a person's most fundamental and vital wants and values, according to the scientist. Conditions for the achievement of potential and self-development include being open to the new, having the capacity for non-standard solutions, having the security of the external environment, and having the freedom to express oneself . Creativity is always domain-specific; specialists decide what constitutes novel and valuable ideas in their field.

There are several ways to look at creativity in the context of education. Considering creativity as the correlation of multiple structural components—methodological, procedural, personal, and panoramic—is the foundation of one approach to the study of creativity in education, which is linked to the introduction of a competency approach. According to this method, creative competence is the capacity for innovative and efficient work, actualized knowledge and experience in uncertain situations with the goal of resolving particular practical issues, preparedness for the adaptive application of learned information, and commitment to ongoing self-improvement and education. The significance of culture, environment, and other factors was noted in all research that have any bearing on the issue of how personality traits

and skill development are related to creativity. Collaboration between higher education, the economic, and cultural policy is necessary for the development of the creative economy, human capital, and innovations. According to John Baer, knowledge, abilities, and attitudes always differ by domain; therefore, the first step in addressing the subject of how to foster creativity is determining which domains to employ. When perspective taking is absent, proximity can foster group innovation, according to research on the topic of creative collaborative teams. Despite the fact that higher education institutions are vital to a changing world, some researchers worry that current curricula do not adequately prepare students for the workforce or the economy, that the study of creativity is underappreciated, and that higher education institutions' creative potential is an underutilized asset of the knowledge-based economy. The authors propose the use of transdisciplinary educational approaches to address this issue by incorporating curriculum-based trainings in creative thinking and research experiences. While analyzing creativity as it is typically incorporated into educational procedures, Soon Ye Hwang contends that creativity should be viewed as a fundamental aspect of human existence and daily experience, suggesting that this kind of approach will foster.

There is a relationship between instructor creativity and student creativity. The degree of creativity exhibited by teachers is correlated with how highly they regard the qualities of their pupils that are linked to creativity; that is, the more creative the teacher, the more admirable the qualities of his students that are linked to creativity. Additionally, creativity is linked to a teacher's leadership style and how he views his pupils. Professors and students have different perspectives on and comprehensions of creativity. While professors perceive student creativity through expressions of self-reflection, independent decision-making, curiosity and motivation, producing and developing something new, students primarily identify creativity as a trait of a person or process. The study aimed at investigating how architects and product designers perceive and understand creativity.

According to the study, under specific circumstances, a variety of elements influence the creation of pupils' creativity. These are, first and foremost, prerequisites for attending university. Students' level of creativity is influenced by their involvement in creative activities and the academic environment. The interdisciplinarity of scientific research, which necessitates the coordination of creative processes throughout the creation of foundational knowledge, highly specialized abilities, and universal human traits, is another of the factors that contribute to the formation of creativity. It is now evident that nurturing creativity is essential in light of the ensuing basic education. Professional talents should be fully complemented by creativity. It has been observed that studying humanities subjects fosters creativity growth. Thus, one of the primary objectives of university instructors' work is the growth of students' creativity. The type and extent to which students' creativity develops depends on their aptitude, individual inventiveness, and the use of cutting-edge teaching strategies. Increasing motivation for the growth of creativity is another aspect of engaging students with research projects. Furthermore, in order to foster the originality of the educational process, university administration should take a comprehensive approach to the development of creativity in every area and at all managerial level.

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